

MODERN AUDIO RECORDINGS IN TEACHING THE CATEGORY OF ASPECT IN RUSSIAN VERBS

Mamchich Natalia Nikolaevna

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Lecturer at the
Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
University of Science and Technology

Abstract. The article is devoted to the use of authentic audio materials in teaching the category of aspect in Russian verbs. Considering the semantics of the perfective aspect solely as the achievement of a limit, completeness, or result is insufficient when studying the semantics of verbal action in foreign-language groups. The use of concepts such as semantic classes of verbs (e.g., phase verbs, etc.) in the study of the perfective aspect, as well as the method of paraphrasing, is highly effective and ensures that non-native students are able to recognize the perfective aspect. It is also important for teachers of pedagogical disciplines to rationally determine the role and place of audio recordings in the training of a teacher of Russian. The use of these technical means is most effective when addressing such topics as principles and methods of teaching, vocational training, and career guidance.

Keywords. Semantics of verbal action, phase verbs, paraphrasing method, use of modern audio recordings, execution of four-beat pause exercises, rational determination of the role and place of audio recordings in the training of a Russian language teacher, unity, interconnection, and interdependence of all teaching tools.

Introduction. One of the effective means of studying the Russian language by non-native students is the use of modern audio recordings. This is especially important because listening classes are not included in the university curriculum.

In traditional methods of teaching aspect, the semantics of the perfective aspect is considered as the achievement of a limit, completeness, and result. Such an understanding of the meaning of the perfective aspect is insufficient when studying the semantics of verbal action in foreign-language groups. In reality, the meaning of aspect is richer in content than mere limitation or result. Therefore, focusing a non-native audience on the notions of limitation and result when studying the category of aspect does not ensure the correct recognition of the perfective aspect.

Main part. At present, teaching and methodological materials aimed at training listening skills have appeared, and they can, of course, be used. In a number of textbooks, objective difficulties of listening comprehension and the specifics of its psycholinguistic parameters, formulated by scholars of the Tver scientific school, are taken into account. This, for example, leads authors to a rather logical rejection of written support while listening to texts.

In most textbooks, synchronous written texts are available during listening, and this significantly reduces their methodological value, since in real communication oral speech is very rarely accompanied by synchronous written text (such as a running line on a television screen or the written “dubbing” of foreign feature films). While this may facilitate the process of sound comprehension, it definitely does not contribute to the formation and improvement of listening speech mechanisms and does not ensure the implementation of the leading principle of foreign language teaching—communicativeness, which implies bringing the learning process as close as possible to real communication conditions.

There have also appeared textbooks that use authentic listening texts. However, in general, the situation with the authenticity of instructional texts remains unsatisfactory: out of 13

modern textbooks that declare the goal of teaching listening comprehension, 9 contain either artificially constructed or de-authenticated texts.

The textbook “*Govorit i pokazyvaet Rossiya*” (“Russia Speaks and Shows”) by V.L. Shunikov is intended for foreign students studying Russian. Its aim is to “develop listening skills of unadapted Russian speech.” Synchronous texts are placed at the end of the textbook and become available after listening. A positive aspect of this textbook, in our view, is the implementation of one of the fundamental principles of foreign language teaching: the principle of interconnectedness with other types of speech activity. This is achieved through tasks that involve productive skills such as speaking (retelling, storytelling, searching for and presenting additional topic-related information) and writing (essays, presentations, expert reports).

The textbook “*Listen*” is particularly interesting in the sense that it enables the development of listening skills based on original authentic texts starting from the lowest levels of overall proficiency in Russian as a foreign language. This publication practically refutes the widespread methodological opinion that it is impossible to teach listening at lower levels using authentic texts. In the series of this textbook, linguistic and speech material gradually becomes more complex; however, in not all of the 75 texts included in these books can one observe a clear correlation between topic, genre, and grammar, that is, a deep unity of the text as a higher-order communicative unit.

For example, from a prescriptive text we expect a specific modality: in expressing advice, requests, demands, or orders, corresponding grammatical forms are activated—primarily the imperative mood of the verb, as well as modal constructions with adverbs such as *must*, *necessary*, etc. Thus, a functional-semantic approach to the text is realized. For instance, in a prescriptive dialogue within the topic “Family: Parents and Children,” speakers (parents) actively use imperfective verbs in the imperative form, which corresponds to typical instructional texts that structure farewell situations before a train departure: *Be good! Write! Take care of yourself!*

In the textbook “*Listen!*”, work with texts is preceded by a table in which each fragment is described according to the following parameters:

1. Title of the text and source;
2. Recommended topic;
3. Linguistic characteristics;
4. Relevant language material;
5. Genre and speech specificity.

After analyzing some teaching and methodological materials aimed at listening comprehension published over the past 10 years, we consider it necessary to note that all audio materials can be conditionally divided into two groups.

The first group consists of training exercises aimed at distinguishing sounds, words, and phrases. They are necessary for developing correct pronunciation and proper intonation skills. In class, students learning Russian listen to and repeat audio materials, striving for accurate pronunciation.

The second group consists of listening comprehension tasks. These may include dialogues or texts of varying length and difficulty. They can be used in different ways: for understanding the general meaning and subsequent retelling; for filling in gaps in written exercises; for selecting appropriate utterances in a dialogue, etc. Audio materials help foreign students overcome the so-called “listening barrier.” In addition, audio recordings can be used for dictations after studying a particular grammar topic.

We consider it both possible and effective to use audio recordings in teaching the category of aspect of Russian verbs to non-native students. The use of semantic class concepts of verbs in studying the perfective aspect, such as phase verbs, etc., as well as the paraphrasing method

that confirms a verb's belonging to a certain semantic class and to the perfective aspect, is highly effective and ensures the recognition of the perfective aspect by non-native students.

The method of semantic analysis and paraphrasing can also be applied in Russian language lessons in schools with non-Russian languages of instruction. A real way to develop skills of recognizing and producing aspect in bilingual learners is to abandon invariant definitions of aspect meaning, analyze verbs according to semantic classes, and consistently apply the paraphrasing method.

One of the effective means of implementing the paraphrasing method is the use of modern audio recordings. Two stages of this work can be outlined: listening to audio recordings containing a text and its paraphrase (e.g., *He carries the wardrobe into the room; he moves the wardrobe so that as a result it is located in the room; he carried the wardrobe into the room; he started carrying the wardrobe into the room, carried it and finished carrying it at the moment when the wardrobe was already in the room*); and performing pause-based four-beat exercises based on the text: the first beat—listening to the text; the second—choosing one of two proposed equivalents to the main text; the third—listening to the correct answer provided by the speaker; the fourth—reproducing the final answer by the student.

Conclusion. Summing up the above, the following conclusion can be drawn: authentic audio materials have great potential for solving educational and instructional tasks when properly guided by a teacher. Due to their high informational content, they create an atmosphere of real language communication and are capable of ensuring successful perception of foreign speech by learners, as well as increasing the motivation of non-native students to study the Russian language.

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